

**EFFECT OF HEAT TREATMENT ON THE PROXIMATE PROPERTIES
AND VITAMIN CONTENTS OF CAKE PRODUCED FROM WHEAT-
BEETROOT FLOUR BLENDS**

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DECEMBER 2024

ABSTRACT

The aim of the study was to investigate the effect of heat-treatment (blanching) on the proximate and vitamin content of cake produced from beetroot and wheat flour blends. The blanching was done at range of 65°C, 85°C, and 100°C for 40 minutes. The cake was produced by using the standard procedure for cake production. The proximate, vitamin content and sensory evaluation of cake were also evaluated using standard analytical methods. The results of proximate properties of the cake indicated that samples range from 10.41-12.89%, 0.51-0.87%, 1.32-3.03%, 21.83-31.19%, 16.61-18.14% and 35.43-46.27% of moisture, Ash, fibre, fat, protein and carbohydrate content respectively. The vitamin content of the sample revealed that sample C had higher value of vitamin C and K, sample D (79.31) and sample A (0.0658). The sensory evaluation of the sample showed that the entire samples were accepted but sample A was mostly preferred in term of overall acceptability. Thus, beetroot cake find new avenue for consumption as a health snack.

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CHAPTER ONE

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The bakery industry is one of the largest organized food industries all over the world and in particular biscuits and cookies are one of the most popular products because of their convenience, ready to eat nature, and long shelf life (Sindhuja, *et al.* 2005). Major contributing factors for increasing the demand for baking product consumption is urbanization, reasonable costs, better shelf life, the taste is good enough, and easy transportation for lightweight. The flours obtained from legumes, tubers, and other cereals products can use vegetable protein and dietary fiber sources for enriching the nutrient contents of this bakery produce (Pinki, 2014). Cakes are convenient food products which are sweet and, usually prepared from wheat flour, sugar, shortening, baking powder and eggs as principal ingredients (Atef *et al.*, 2011). The insufficiency of fiber, iron, calcium, antioxidants and folic acid in bakery products especially, in high sugar items such as cakes, can be made by incorporating beetroot powder with wheat flour to make it healthier and more nutritious.

Beetroot is highly acceptable for its rich nutrient contents *viz.* dietary fiber, mineral contents such as iron, potassium, calcium, zinc, and sodium, and vitamin contents such as vitamin A, B6, folic acid, niacin, biotin and C (Pinki, 2014; Bach *et al.*, 2015; da Silva *et al.*, 2016; Singh *et al.*, 2016). Some essential bioactive compounds like carotenoids (Dias *et al.*, 2009), phenolic compounds, saponins, betaine (Jastrebova *et al.*, 2003), betalains (antioxidants), polyphenols and flavonoids (Vali *et al.*, 2007) also present in beetroot powder having anti-cancer and therapeutic properties (Neagu and Barbu, 2014). These compounds are having anti-oxidative (da Silva *et al.*, 2016), hepatoprotective, anticancer and anti-inflammatory activity (Kavalcova *et*

al., 2015), may improve many clinical outcomes such as hypertension, type-2 diabetes, atherosclerosis and dementia (Clifford *et al.*, 2015). Beetroot contains both betaine and nitrate. Betaine is a trimethyl derivative of amino acid glycine which promotes muscular endurance, strength, and power (Hoffman and Ratamess, 2009).

The wheat, which is the major ingredient, a cereal, is cultivated in many parts of the world, but imported by countries with unfavorable climatic conditions. Such importing countries such as Nigeria spend a lot of foreign exchange on the importation of wheat. There is a compelling need to develop an adequate substitute for wheat, as the demand and price of this product could further be increased by the unstable exchange rates. In addition, there is an increasing trend among consumers for functional food products. This has greatly influenced the use of composite flours in which flours from locally grown crops and high protein seeds replace a portion of wheat flour for use in cake production. In the quest for a wheat substitute, flour with better nutritional quality than wheat would be highly desirable, especially in developing countries where malnutrition is prevalent. Food safety system must be priority, so that adequate preparation and thermal processing of food are becoming indispensable factors of proper nutrition. Thanks to new scientific knowledge, humans are increasingly changing their eating habits, and preparing meals has become easier, food contains more quality nutrients, and at the same time preserves the natural taste (Grujic *et al.*, 2010a; Creed 2010; Daniela *et al.*, 2014).

1.1 Justification

Foods with high nutritional value are in great demand for proper functioning of body systems and potential health benefits. As a result, value-added foods or functional foods with higher level of dietary fibre and antioxidant have been developed, especially in bakery products such as cake.

The incorporation of composite flour into traditional wheat-based food products provided additional nutrients from non-wheat material and improved the nutritional value of the products. The utilization of beetroot powder using different heat-treatment with wheat flour in bakery products have not been studied extensively. Therefore, the research was designed to evaluate the effect of substitution of wheat flour with different heat-treated beetroot powder on the chemical and sensory properties of the cake.

1.2 Aim and Objectives

Aim

To produce cake blends of wheat – pretreated beetroot flour

Objectives

The objectives of this study are:

To produce flour from treated and untreated beetroot pulp

To determine the proximate composition of the cake produced

To determine the vitamin profile of the cake produced

To carry out the organoleptic assessment on the cake produced

CHAPTER TWO

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Vegetables

Vegetables are defined as the fresh parts of plants which, raw, cooked, canned or processed in some other way, provide suitable human nutrition. Fruits of perennial trees are not considered to be vegetables. Ripe seeds are also excluded (peas, beans, cereal grains, etc.). From a botanical point of view, vegetables can be divided into algae (seaweed), mushrooms, root vegetables (carrots), tubers (potatoes, yams), bulbs and stem or stalk (kohlrabi, parsley), leafy (spinach), inflorescence (broccoli), seed (green peas) and fruit (tomato) vegetables.

2.2 Pretreatment of vegetables

2.2.1 Thermal blanching

Thermal blanching is widely used prior to drying, its primary goal is to inactivate the enzymes involved in the spoilage of fresh agro-products, in addition to reduce the microbial load of products so as to improve its conservation, to soften tissues for facilitating drying process, and to eliminate intracellular air to prevent oxidation.

2.2.1.1 Conventional hot water blanching

Hot water blanching is a common pretreatment used prior to drying; it involves immersing fresh products into hot water at a constant temperature ranging from 70 to 100 °C for several minutes (Guida et al., 2013). Generally, hot water blanching has been used to prevent

quality deterioration by inactivating the enzymes, destroying microorganisms, or expelling intercellular air from the tissues (Mukherjee and Chattopadhyay, 2007). Meanwhile, it also helps to accelerate drying rate by changing the physical properties of the samples such as the permeability of the membranes, dissociating the wax on and forming offline cracks on the skin of products (Mukherjee and Chattopadhyay, 2007).

Currently, conventional hot water blanching is the most popular and commercially adopted method, because of its simple equipment and easy operation. It has been widely applied on pretreatment of agro-products to enhance the drying rate and improve the product quality. During hot water blanching process, the marked deterioration in food quality is also implicated in oxidase inactivation, especially with the development of cooked off-flavors, color alteration and the loss of thermo-sensitive compounds. On the one hand, processing for agro-products with complete inactivation of oxidase is more than adequate to those with activity of peroxidase left, as the quality of the blanched products may be better than un-blanched (Aguero *et al.*, 2008).

2.2.1.2 Steam blanching

To minimize nutrients especially the water-soluble nutrients and solid content dissolves into hot water and reduce the wastewater, steam blanching systems were developed to replace hot water blanching. It is believed that the steam blanching contributes to retention of most minerals and water-soluble components as compared with water blanching, due to its negligible leaching effect. Compared to hot water blanching, steam blanching for equal treated time resulted in significantly higher ascorbic acid retention (Lin and Brewer, 2005). Lin and Brewer (2005) reported that, steam blanched peas had higher ascorbic acid content (22mg/100 g) than water blanched peas (14 mg/100 g), slightly lower than non-blanched peas (29 mg/100 g). Steam

blanching gave rise to carrots with higher retention of vitamin C (81.2%) than those blanched in water at 60 °C (1.3%).

2.2.1.3 Superheated steam impingement blanching

With increasing in demand of high-quality products, it is very important to minimize nutrient loss during the pretreatment, the traditional hot water and steam blanching should be replaced by novel techniques. Superheated steam impingement blanching (SSIB), also called high humidity hot air impingement blanching (HHAIB), is a recently developed thermal treatment technology, which combines the advantages of super-heated steam blanching and impingement technologies. SSIB has higher enthalpy, transfer heat rate and energy efficiency, the heat transfer coefficient of SSIB was about 1403 W/(m²°K) with velocity of 14.4 m/s, temperature of 135 °C, and relative humidity of 35%, respectively, it is about 12 times of that of hot air impingement at the same temperature and velocity. SSIB has advantages in a uniform, rapid and energy-efficient blanching, as well as better product quality retain. SSIB possesses an excellent capability of preventing browning and maintaining color by inactivating oxidase rapidly, increasing drying rate by modifying the skin and pulp tissue (Gao and Xiao, 2008).

Recently, SSIB technology has been applied to several vegetables and fruits pretreatment, applied HHAIB processing (110 °C, RH 30%–40%, air velocity 14.0±0.5 m/s) to red pepper, results showed that POD activity rapidly decreased to 7% after 120 s; the drying time for blanched samples were reduced by 17 h, as compared to non-blanched peppers. Bai *et al.* (2013a) observed that the SSIB completely inactivated PPO within 7 min at 90–120 °C of apple quarters with thickness of 3.8 cm, while infrared radiation at 4000 W/ m², fully inactivated PPO of 1.3 cm apple slices also needed 7min; the retention of vitamin C more than 11% when

blanched at 90 C for 7 min. Bai *et al.* (2013b) also reported that SSIB effectively inactivated PPO activity at 110 °C for 90s, reduced drying time by 12–25 h and improved color quality of seedless grapes, which presented as desirable green–yellow or green color.

2.2.1.4 Microwave heating

Microwaves (MW) are electromagnetic wave with frequency varies within 300 MHz to 300 GHz, and wavelengths range from 1 mm to 1 m. Microwave heating, as radiofrequency heating, is based on the use of electromagnetic waves of certain frequencies to generate heat in a material, the electric energy conversion is evaluated to be approximately 50% and efficiency of MW heating can reach up to 65%. During microwave heating, the materials absorb microwave energy and convert it into heat by dielectric heating caused by molecular dipole rotation and agitation of charged ions within a high frequency alternating electric field, the heat generated volumetrically throughout a product rather than relying on the slow conduction of heat through its surface. Compared to conventional heating, microwave blanching (MWB) has faster heating rates as microwave heating takes place within the wet biological materials, and it increases with the effective output power used. MWB requires lower processing time, has higher heating efficiency and nutrient retention compared to conventional methods (Krokida *et al.*, 2000).

2.3 Beetroot

Beetroot (*Beta vulgaris L.*) is crop belonging to the Chenopodiaceae family having, bright crimson colour. It is famous for its juice value and medicinal properties; and known by several common names like beet, chard, spinach beet. sea beet. garden beet, white beet and *Chukander* (in Hindi). Beetroot gives the best value from June to November, and for storing, the beetroot leaves should be cut 50 mm above the root. They will keep for 4-5 days when

refrigerated in the vegetable crisper. Beetroot 'Boltardy' is one of the best varieties which produce large round shaped tender roots of deep red colour and fresh sweet flavour. Beetroot 'Burpees Golden' is globe shaped and golden orange in color. It is biennials if roots are grown for seed. It was not cultivated until the 3rd century and not developed until the 19th century by German and French breeders.

Beetroot is the name used by the British and some other English speaking countries including Australia and the New Zealand for the vegetable that Americans in the USA call beets a type of food. Beetroots main benefits are that it contains no fat, very few calories and is a great source of fiber. The best quality and root color are obtained when the air temperature ranges between 10 and 18 °C. Abundant rainfall, nitrogen fertilizer and high temperatures provide for rapid development which leads to white rings in the interior of the beetroot. The minimum soil temperature for beet germination is 5 °C, with an optimum range of 10 to 30 °C, an optimum temperature of 30 °C and a maximum temperature of 35 °C. Beets require a cold period of 2 weeks at 4 to 10 °C or longer to initiate flowers. Beets will tolerate frosts and mild freezes. Beets prefer deep, friable, well drained, sandy loams to silt loams. High organic matter in the soil is desirable and will help ensure an adequate moisture supply. The beet has a fairly large root system extending downward in the soil 1 m or more unless restricted. Beets are used for bunched greens, bunched roots, and beetroots and by processors for many products.

Beetroots for processing and fresh markets are harvested mainly in September and October. A yield of 20,000 kg per hectare is possible (Beetroot, 2003). The roots and greens therefore are great for women in general and for those planning pregnancy. The fresh beetroot and sliced beetroot are shown in Fig 2.1.

Beetroot is a good tonic food for health. The main markets for beet greens and bunched beets are roadside, farmers markets and deliveries to wholesalers. The market for beetroot is not a large market but it is significant. With storage the marketing season may be extended for roots. Beta vulgaris var. rubra revealed significant tumor inhibitory effects in skin and lung cancer. These findings suggest that beetroot ingestion can be a useful means to prevent development and progression of cancer. But extracts of beetroot also showed some antimicrobial activity on *Staphylococcus aureus* and on *Escherichia coli* and also antiviral effect was observed (Rauha *et al.*, 2000).

Today the beetroot is still championed as a universal panacea. One of the most controversial examples is the official position of the South African health minister on the treatment of AIDS. Dr Manto Tshabalala-Msimang, health minister under Thabo Mbeki, had been nicknamed "Dr Beetroot" for promoting beets and other vegetables over antiretroviral AIDS medicines, which she considers toxic (Blandy, 2006). Beetroot is one of the original 'super foods'. Beetroot is a naturally environmentally friendly crop, rarely needing treatment with pesticides. Up to 10 per cent of beetroot is sugar, but it is released slowly into the body rather than the sudden rush that results from eating chocolate.

The usually deep-red roots of beetroot are eaten boiled either as a cooked vegetable, or cold as a salad after cooking and adding oil and vinegar, or raw and shredded, either alone or combined with any salad vegetable. A large proportion of the commercial production is processed into boiled and sterilized beets or into pickles. In Eastern Europe beet soup, such as cold borscht, is a popular dish. Yellow-coloured beetroots are grown on a very small scale for home consumption (Grubben *et al.*, 2004).

Effects of a commercially available beetroot juice on inflammation is strongly involved in the development and progression of several clinical conditions including coronary heart disease and cancer, beneficial effect of beetroot extract may relate to this anti-inflammatory capacity (Winkler *et al.*, 1990). Volume 01, No.3, March 2015 Page22

Hughes and Mitchell (2006) reported that both shallow and deep beds of diced beetroot have been studied, variables investigated being D.B.T. 120-200 °F (49–93 °C); air flow (6-12 lb of air/sq. ft /min); W.B.D. 10-70 °F (-12 to 21 °C). Drying rates in shallow beds were found to depend largely on the D.B.T., the W.B.D. and air-flow rate having a less marked effect. A prediction method used to determine the drying times of deep beds of diced beetroot in the moisture content range 8 to 0.1 was applied and found to be accurate to $\pm M 9.0$ %. Moisture distribution in a single slice of beetroot during drying has also been studied. Pickled beets are a traditional food of the American South. It is also common in Australia and New Zealand for pickled beetroot to be consumed on a burger. Garden beet juice is a popular health food betanins, obtained from the roots, are used industrially as red food colourants e.g. to improve the colour of tomato paste, sauces, desserts, jams and jellies, ice cream, sweets and cereals. Red beet also makes a rich, red, Burgundy style wine.

The wild sea beet is the earliest form of beetroot and is supposed to be the source for all the different beetroot varieties available today. The vegetable was native to the Indian and British coastlines. The beetroot, as we know it today, was only developed in the sixteenth century. Roots can be round shaped, cylindrical or tapered. Their colour can be white, yellow or red according to the colour of the flesh. The leafy tops can also be used as a tasty spinach substitute.

2.4 Historical of Background

Beets are native to the Mediterranean. Although the leaves have been eaten since before written history, the beetroot was generally used medicinally and did not become a popular food until French recognized their potential in the 1800's. Beet powder is used as a coloring agent for many foods. Some frozen pizzas use beet powder to color the tomato sauce. The most common garden beet is a deep ruby red in color, but yellow, white, and even candy-striped are available in specialty markets. Outside the United States, beets are generally referred to as beetroot. It is estimated that about two-thirds of commercial beet crops end up canned.

They state the earliest written mention of the beet comes from 8th century Mesopotamia (Hopf *et al.*, 2000). The Greek Peripatetic Theophrastus later describes the beet as similar to the radish, while Aristotle also mentions the plant. Zohary and Hopf also argue that it is very probable that beetroot cultivars were also grown at the time, and some Roman recipes support this. Later English and German sources show that beetroots were commonly cultivated in Medieval Europe (Hopf *et al.*, 2000).

(a)

(b)

Fig. 2.1: (a) and (b) shows fresh and sliced beetroot respectively

2.5 Origin and Distribution of Beetroot

The beetroot is indigenous to Asia Minor and Europe. They were first used for food about the third century AD although they had been grown for thousands of years for medicinal purposes. Beetroot has been regarded as a laxative, a cure for bad breath, coughs and headaches, and even as an aphrodisiac. It is grown widely in Germany and France and in lesser amounts in other European countries, Africa, Asia, and South America. Beetroot is now a popular salad vegetable.

2.6 Morphology of the plant

Roots: The beetroot is a true biennial, producing thickened root and a rosette of leaves during the first year and flowers and seeds the second year. Beetroots are mainly grown for their swollen roots.

Stem: The stem is short and plate, producing simple leaves that are arranged in a The stem is short and plate producing simple leaves that are arranged in a stem is short and plate, producing simple leaves that are arranged in a closed spiral.

Leaves: the leaves are heart shaped. The leaves can also be eaten as spinach.

Flower: Flowers are very small with a diameter of 3 to 5 mm and are produced in dense spikes. They are green or tinged reddish, with five petals.

Fruits: the fruit is a cluster of hard nut lets and dark colour. (Anonymous) ^[12].

Plant description

Kingdom: *Plantae*

Order: *Caryophyllales*

Family: *Chenopodiaceae*

Genus: *Beta*

Binomial name: *Beta vulgaris*, L

2.7 Varieties of Beetroot

1. Detroit Dark Red

The variety produces perfectly round beet with smooth uniform red skin. The interior colour is dark red with light red zoning. Flesh is tender and fine grained, tops small; leaves dark green tinged with maroon. It is a heavy yielding cultivar. Crop matures in 80-100 days.

2. Crimson Globe

Beet is globular to flatten in shape, medium red in colour with small shoulders. Flesh medium dark Crimson red with indistinct zoning top. Leaves are medium-large, bright green with and have a higher maroon shade. It is a high yielding cultivar.

3. Ooty 1, Crimson Globe, Red Ball, Crosby Egyptian are the popular varieties.

2.8 Nutritional composition of beetroot (*Beta vulgaris L.*)

The beetroot species *Beta vulgaris L.* is considered a good source of dietary fibre, minerals (potassium, sodium, iron, copper, magnesium, calcium, phosphorus and zinc), vitamins (retinol, ascorbic acid and B-complex), antioxidants, betalains and phenolic compounds, and possesses high nutritional value due to its high glucose content, in the form of sucrose (van Velzen *et al.*, 2008, USDA, 2013). According to data presented by the United States Department of Agriculture (USDA) for macronutrients, 100 g of raw beetroot has an energy value of 43 kcal, 9.56 g of carbohydrates, 1.61 g of proteins, 0.17 g of total lipids, 2.8 g of total dietary fibre and 6.76 g of total sugars (USDA, 2013).

2.9 Chemical Composition of Beetroot

2.9.1 Bioactive beetroot compounds

Plants are generally considered important sources of substances that perform bioactive functions, favouring human health, good organ function, disease control and contributing to longevity (Sabaté, 2003). Insufficient intake of bioactive compounds from plant sources is considered an important risk factor for the development of chronic and non-communicable diseases.

Bioactive compounds may have different physiological targets and mechanisms of action, Many of these compounds show antioxidant action due to their potential for oxi-reduction of certain molecules, while others have the capacity to compete for active enzymatic and receptor sites in various sub-cellular structures or may modulate the expression of genes encoding proteins involved in intracellular mechanisms of defence against oxi-degenerative processes of molecules and cellular structures (Liu, 2004).

2.9.1.1 Betalains

Beetroots are a major source of betalains, classified as one of the 10 plants with the highest antioxidant activity, determined by the IC50 value, i.e. the extract's ability to reduce low-density lipoproteins (LDL) oxidation by 50%. Betalains are present in the tuberous part of the plant, conferring its red-purple coloration, and act as antioxidant agents (Ravichandran *et al.*, 2011). In addition, anti-inflammatory, hepatic protective and anti-cancer properties have also been attributed to this class of compounds (Winkler *et al.*, 2005).

Betalains are heterocyclic compounds and water-soluble nitrogen pigments responsible for conferring various types of coloration in flowers, vegetables and fruits (Volp *et al.*, 2009). Betanin, a compound belonging to one of the betalain classes, has excellent stability at pH 4 and 5 and reasonable stability between pH 3 and 4 and pH 5 and 7. The stability of these molecules is affected by factors such as exposure to light, high temperature (i.e. cooking processes), high water activity and the presence of oxygen. In addition, they can also be degraded by enzymes, such as polyphenoloxidases and peroxidases, released during food processing. Betanins are formed from a common precursor, betalamic acid, with more than 50 structures identified so far. Furthermore, these pigments are present in acid form due to the presence of several carboxyl groups and, are, therefore not classified as alkaloids (Escribano *et al.*, 2002).

2.9.1.2 Phenolic compounds

Phenolic compounds present in plants are derived from the aromatic amino acid phenylalanine and are formed by two aromatic rings (A and B), linked by three carbon atoms that form an oxygenated heterocycle (ring C) (Crozier *et al.*, 2006). These compounds are secondary metabolites in fruits and vegetables and are generally involved in the defence against

pathogens and/or against ultraviolet radiation. In addition, many volatile phenolic compounds are responsible for the assignment of sensory characteristics, or flavour, in various foods commonly included in the human diet (Aherne and O'brien, 2002).

Beetroots are also an adequate source of phenolic compounds, and several studies have been carried out on the identification and evaluation of the antioxidant content and capacity of phenolic compounds present in this vegetable. Previous studies have shown that beetroot tuber juice is particularly rich in phenolic compounds and that these components remain active even after *in vitro* digestion trials. Kujala *et al.* (2002) reported the presence of ferulic acid, flavonoids and phenolic amides, mainly in beetroot skin, which confer strong antioxidant activity to this food.

Flavonoid concentrations and species present in beetroot formulations should be better evaluated so that the intake of this vegetable in the human diet is as efficient as possible, since flavonoids can be lost in vegetable processing. In a recent study, Silva *et al.* (2016) developed a beetroot gel formulation, obtained from beetroot juice and powder, enriched in flavonoid content. While the beetroot juice contained 0.42 mg of quercetin equivalents per gram (QE/g), phenolic compounds in the gel were three times higher, reaching 1.37 mg QE/g. Guldiken *et al.* (2016) determined flavonoid concentrations in beetroots processed through different forms of cooking, such as oven drying, canning, puree, processed juice, jelly and fresh beetroots, and found values ranging from 1.26 to 2.61 mg of rutin equivalents (RE)/g.

Phenolic compound composition and concentrations also vary according to the cultivar. Kujala *et al.* (2016) studied four distinct beetroot cultivars by high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) and HPLC- electrospray ionisation-mass spectrometry (HPLC-ESI-

MS) and NMR techniques and identified four flavonoids, betagarin, betavulgarin, cochliophilin A and dihydroisorhamnetin, whereas Georgiev *et al.* (2010) identified the presence of catechin hydrate, epicatechin and rutin. The importance of flavonoids in the human diet has been ascribed to their horticultural effect, contributing to chemoprevention of DNA damage caused by several carcinogenic factors (Georgiev *et al.*, 2010).

2.9.1.3 Saponins

These compounds vary extensively in structure and are widely distributed in plants. They are triterpene glycosides wherein the aglycone is covalently linked to one or two sugar chains through a glycosidic ester (C-28) or ether (to C-3) bond. Saponins exhibit several biological activities, such as anti-viral, anti-diabetic and anti-haemolytic properties, and have been, therefore, well studied (Mikołajczyk-Batora *et al.*, 2015).

Few studies are available regarding the evaluation of saponin content in beetroots. The occurrence of saponins in these species was characterized in a study conducted by Mroczek (2012), where 11 saponins derived from oleanoic acids were identified using reverse phase liquid chromatography coupled with electrospray ionization mass spectrometry (LC-ESI/MS/MS). As with flavonoids, the content and species of saponins may vary according to the cultivar, with concentrations varying from 7.66 to 12.2 mg/g dry weight in three different beetroot cultivars (*Beta vulgaris L.*). Oleanoic acid is of importance among the saponins identified in the beet, since it is capable of causing a marked hypoglycemic effect. Saponin content may also vary according to beetroot processing. In the study conducted by Silva *et al.* (2016), saponin content was almost three times higher in beetroot gel compared to juice, of 22 and 8.22 mg/g, respectively.

2.9.2 Health Benefits of Beetroot

Betalains have antiviral effects (Strack *et al.*, 2003) and also can inhibit the cell proliferation of human tumour cells (Reddy *et al.* 2005). Consumption of red beet which are rich source of antioxidants can contribute to protection from age related diseases. Zitnanova *et al.* (2006) red beet is one of the most potent vegetable with respect to antioxidant activity. Significant amount of vitamin C, Vitamin B1, B2, niacin, B6, B12 are found in beetroot, while the leaves are an excellent source of vitamin A consuming beetroot helps in curing many diseases such as anemia, blood pressure, cancer, dandruff, gastric ulcers, kidney ailments, liver toxicity or bile ailments like jaundice, hepatitis, food poisoning, diarrhoea or vomiting.

In addition to their usefulness as colorants, betalains play an important role in human health because of their pharmacological activities such as antioxidant, anti-cancer, anti-lipidemic and antimicrobial. In addition to the health beneficial compounds, however, beetroots also contain significant quantities of oxalic acid. Oxalic acid is a strong metal ion chelator interfering with iron and calcium metabolism and can lead to the formation of nephritis (Holmes and Assimos, 2004).

2.9.3 Medicinal Benefits of Beetroot

Beetroot detoxifies the liver: The Researchers claims that compounds found in beetroot detoxify the liver and have the ability to cure diseases of the digestive system in human being. It encourages liver cleansing, improves liver functioning, and protects it from excessive alcohol consumption. Beetroot juice has the ability to cure liver and kidney diseases, particularly the buildup of fatty deposits in the liver caused by alcohol abuse, protein deficiency or diabetes. Beetroot juice can also dissolve kidney stones and prevent its pain.

Beetroot combats high blood pressure: People who used to drink two cups of beetroot juice can lower blood pressure within about 60 minutes of drinking the juice with a peak drop occurring 3-4 hours after ingestion. The reduction in blood pressure continued to be observed until up to 24 hours after the juice was ingested.

Beetroot boosts Glutathione levels in the body: It has been found that beetroot increase the body's production of glutathione. This substance, which is naturally produced by the human body, is known as the body's master antioxidant and detoxifier. Virtually every cell of the body uses it to neutralize the toxins.

Beetroot juice can provide protection against birth defects: It is a very good source of folic acid (also called folate). To prevent the possibility of birth defects, doctors recommend the B vitamin folate in a pregnant woman's diet. Folic Acid is a key vitamin for proper fetus development as it helps in the proper development of the infant's spinal column and optimal brain development. Folate is very involved in the production of new cells and the maintenance of existing cells.

Lower the cholesterol level: One of the important health benefits of beet juice is its ability to lower bad cholesterol levels and raise healthy LDL cholesterol levels in the body.

Anemia: Beets are rich in iron, which is easily assimilated by the body. They build up the hemoglobin and cleanse the blood.

Antioxidant: The deep, red pigment betacyanin is a powerful antioxidant and protects against several types of cancer.

Cancer: Dr. Alexander Ferenczi successfully treated cancer patients with either raw beet roots or juiced.

Colon Health: Beets are full of fiber, which helps to move wastes through the intestines and helps to prevent constipation. Also, the antioxidants found in beets protect against colon cancer.

Constipation: The high fiber content of beets makes them excellent to relieve constipation.

Eye Health: Traditionally, beetroot juice has been used to improve eye health and fatigue.

Heart Disease: The abundance of vitamins and minerals in beetroot helps to protect against heart disease.

Inflammation Reduction: The compound called betalaine found in red beets can reduce inflammation in joints, bones, and blood vessels. This reduction in inflammation helps those suffering from asthma and osteoporosis.

Menstrual Problems: Beetroot juice has been shown to help correct menstrual problems in women.

Pregnant Women: Beets are high in folic acid which helps to prevent birth defects in your unborn baby. Folic acid is important whenever your body is actively making new cells when healing after physical trauma or when children are growing.

Stamina Increase: Drinking beetroot juice boosts stamina and can increase workout time by causing a reduction in the uptake of your oxygen, thus increasing stamina. The natural and unprocessed abundance of carbohydrates found in beets are an excellent source of energy for the body. When the Betalaine pigment is absorbed into the blood it can reportedly increase the oxygen-carrying ability of the blood by up to 400 per cent (Anonymous 2011).

2.9.4 Harvesting and Handling

Harvesters used for other root crops are used for beets. Harvest under dry weather and soil conditions. Ensure that soil and debris are minimized in the bulk bins so that the beets have sufficient fresh air in storage.

2.9.5 Processing and Uses of beetroot

Young leaves of the garden beet are sometimes used for eating. The midribs of Swiss chard are eaten boiled while the whole leaf blades are eaten as spinach beet. In some parts of Africa, the whole leaf blades are usually prepared with the major as one dish (Grubben *et al.*, 2004).

The leaves and stems of young plants are steamed briefly and eaten as a vegetable, older leaves and stems are stir-fried. The usually deep-red roots of garden beet are eaten boiled either as a cooked vegetable or cold as a salad after cooking and adding oil and vinegar. A large proportion of the commercial production is processed into boiled and sterilized beets or into pickles. In Eastern Europe beet soup, such as cold soup, is a popular dish. Yellow-coloured Garden beets are grown on a very small scale for home consumption. Beetroot can be peeled, steamed, and then eaten warm with butter as a delicacy; cooked, pickled, and then eaten cold as a condiment; or peeled, shredded raw, and then eaten as a salad. Pickled beets are a traditional food of the American South.

The beetroot apart from consumption in its fresh form, is also a valuable vegetable used in the food industry to produce dried and frozen food, non-concentrated and concentrated juices as well as natural colorants (betalains) used as additives in food manufacturing. Beetroot peel contained higher antioxidant compounds thus promising a more intense utilization of the peels in food and nutraceutical. Beetroot pigment is used commercially as a food dye (Singh *et al.*, 2014).

The aim in food processing of beetroot is to increase its shelf life, so that it is available in the off season also. Many processed value-added products are prepared from beetroot vegetable.

2.9.5.1 Candy preparation

A whole fruit or its pieces impregnated with cane sugar or glucose syrup and subsequently drained free of syrup and dried, is known as candied fruit. This process is also known as osmotic dehydration. The process for making candied fruit is practically similar to that for preserves. The only difference is that the fruit is impregnated with syrup having a higher per cent of sugar or glucose. A certain amount (25-30 per cent) of invert sugar or glucose, viz., confectioner's glucose (corn syrup, crystal syrup or commercial glucose), dextrose or invert sugar is substituted for cane sugar. The total sugar content of the impregnated fruit is kept at about 75 per cent to prevent fermentation. The syrup left after the candying process can be used for candying of another batch of same kind of fruit after suitable dilution for sweetening product (Anonymous, 2013).

In candy-making, controlling the rate and extent of sugar crystallization provides a vast array of different texture. These range from the soft textures of fondants and fudges, where crystallization is minimized, to hard candies where crystallization results in a desired grainy or crystalline structure. The sugar is an essential to perceive the texture of foods commonly referred to as 'mouth feel'. Considering the importance of acceptability of osmotically dehydrated product in the process of candy making, it is necessary to fix the level of sugar gain and moisture content in the final product, so that it is acceptable by the consumers. Beetroot pigment is used commercially as a food dye. It changes colour when heated so can only be used in ice-cream, sweets and other confectionary, but it is both cheap and has no

2.9.5.2 Juice Ingredients

Beetroot juice is not only blessed with a beautiful color but also packed with nutrients. A detailed view of this parcel comes out to be like:

- **Vitamins:** Beetroots are a good source of folic acid and vitamin C. It also contains small amounts of vitamins B₁, B₂, B₃, and vitamin A in the form of beta-carotene.
- **Minerals:** Rich in calcium, magnesium, phosphorus, potassium, and sodium. Also, smaller amounts of iron, zinc, copper, manganese, and selenium.
- **Amino acids:** While raw beets are mostly water and carbohydrate, they also contain small amounts of all the amino acids (protein).
- **Calories:** One 2" (5 cm) beetroot contains 35 calories.
- **Antioxidants:** Its carotenoids and flavanoids can help reduce the oxidation of LDL cholesterol which could lead to damaged artery walls and ultimately heart attacks and strokes.
- **Anti-carcinogenic color:** The deep red color of beetroot comes from betacyanin. This prevents from colon cancer.
- **Silica:** The rich stock of silica in it does perfect utilization of calcium in the body and is also required for healthy skin, hair, nails and bo

2.9.5.3 Specifications of Beetroot Powder

1. Chemical/Physical Properties (as manufactured):

- Colour: Red to purple;

- Specific Gravity: 0.7~0.8;
- Color Intensity (O.D. @ 537 nm): 0.3~0.4;
- Dilution: 1:1000 in 0.1 mole;
- Citric acid colour pigment: 0.3~0.4 %;
- Consistency: Free Flowing Powder;
- Solubility: Soluble all parts in water.

2. Chemical analysis copper content, mg/kg, Max: 20; Arsenic content, mg/kg, Max: 3; Lead content, mg/kg, Max: 5; Heavy metal, mg/kg, Max: 30.

3. Microbiological Properties Standard Plate Count/g, Max: 200 Yeast/g, Max: 5 Mold/g, Max: 5 E. coli/g; Nil Salmonella/25 g. Volume 01, No.3, March 2015 Page25

4. Packaging: 20 kg in HDPE drums or 15 kg in corrugated boxes.

5. Storage conditions: Protect from any exposure to air, light & heat. Do not freeze.

6. Shelf-life: Min 6 months.

2.9.6 Origin of Wheat

The first cultivation of wheat occurred about 10 000 years ago, as part of the ‘Neolithic Revolution’, which saw a transition from hunting and gathering of food to settled agriculture. These earliest cultivated forms were diploid (genome AA) (einkorn) and tetraploid (genome AABB) (emmer) wheats and their genetic relationships indicate that they originated from the south-eastern part of Turkey. Cultivation spread to the Near East by about 9000 years ago when hexaploid bread wheat made its first appearance (Feldman, 2001).

The earliest cultivated forms of wheat were essentially landraces selected by farmers from wild populations, presumably because of their superior yield and other characteristics, an early and clearly non-scientific form of plant breeding! However, domestication was also associated with the selection of genetic traits that separated them from their wild relatives. This domestication syndrome has been discussed in detail by others, but two traits are of sufficient importance to mention here. The first is the loss of shattering of the spike at maturity, which results in seed loss at harvesting. This is clearly an important trait for ensuring seed dispersal in natural populations and the non-shattering trait is determined by mutations at the Br (brittle rachis) locus (Feldman, 2001).

The second important trait is the change from hulled forms, in which the glumes adhere tightly to the grain, to free-threshing naked forms. The free forms arose by a dominant mutant at the Qlocus which modified the effects of recessive mutations at the Tg (tenacious glume) locus.

Cultivated forms of diploid, tetraploid, and hexaploid wheat all have a tough rachis apart from the spelt form of bread wheat. Similarly, the early domesticated forms of einkorn, emmer, and spelt are all hulled, whereas modern forms of tetraploid and hexaploid wheat are free-threshing.

Whereas einkorn and emmer clearly developed from the domestication of natural populations, bread wheat has only existed in cultivation, having arisen by hybridization of cultivated emmer with the unrelated wild grass *Triticum tauschii* (also called *Aegilops tauschii* and *Ae. squarosa*).

This hybridization probably occurred several times independently with the novel hexaploid (genome AABBDD) being selected by farmers for its superior properties. The evolution of modern wheats, The genetic changes during domestication mean that modern wheats are unable to survive wild in competition with better adapted species. This was elegantly demonstrated by John Bennet Lawes in the 1880s when he decided to allow part of the famous long-term Broadbalk experiment at Rothamsted to return to its natural state.

2.9.7 Classification of Wheat

The primary use of wheat is to produce food for humans. Grain that is not good enough for human food is used for animal feed. Many different food products are made from the different classes of wheat. Durum wheat is used to make pastas. Hard red wheat is used to make loaf bread and other products. The soft red winter wheat grown in Ohio is used to make cookies, cakes, donuts, and other fine pastries. Often, flour from different classes of wheat is blended to make special flours for unique food products. The various classes of wheat are described here.

1. **Durum Wheat:** the hardest of all U.S. wheat, is seeded in the spring and contains a high amount of protein (12–16%), which is good for pasta products — macaroni, spaghetti, and other noodles. Durum wheat is grown mainly in North Dakota and has subclasses such as Hard Amber Durum, Amber Durum, and Durum wheat. Total acreage is about 3.2 million acres.

2. **Hard Red Spring Wheat:** contains the highest protein content (13–16.5%) making it an excellent bread wheat with superior milling and baking characteristics. Hard red spring wheat is grown mostly in Montana, the Dakotas, and Minnesota. This wheat is seeded in the spring and may have either a hard or a soft endosperm. Subclasses are Dark Northern Spring, Northern Spring, and Red Spring wheat. Total acreage is about 13.8 million acres.
3. **Hard Red Winter Wheat:** is the class of wheat used mostly for bread and all-purpose flour. This wheat is fall-seeded, has medium to high protein content (10–13.5%), and can have either hard or soft endosperm. Hard red winter wheat accounts for more than 40% of the U.S. wheat crop and half of U.S. wheat exports.
4. This wheat is produced in the Great Plains, between the Mississippi River and the Rocky Mountains, and from Texas to the Dakotas and Montana. It has a wide range of protein and good milling and baking qualities. The flour is used to produce bread, rolls, some sweet goods, and all-purpose flour. Total acreage is about 23 million acres.
5. **Hard White Wheat:** is the newest class of wheat to be grown in the United States. Hard white wheat is closely related to red wheat except for the color genes and has a milder, sweeter flavor, equal fiber, and similar milling and baking qualities. Hard white wheat is used in yeast breads, hard rolls, bulgur, tortillas, and oriental noodles. This wheat is used in domestic markets and is exported in limited amounts. There are no subclasses. Total acreage is about 0.3 million acres.
6. **Soft Red Winter Wheat:** is seeded in the fall, has a low to medium protein content with soft endosperm, and is used to make cakes, pastries, flat breads, and crackers. It is grown east of the Mississippi and has no subclasses. Ohio is the leading producer of soft red

winter wheat followed by Arkansas, Illinois, and Missouri. Ohio wheat is known for making higher-quality flour than that coming from any other soft red winter wheat-producing state. Total acreage is about 13.0 million acres.

7. **Soft White Wheat:** is used much the same way as soft red wheat (for bakery products other than bread) and is grown mostly in the Pacific Northwest and to a lesser extent in California, Wisconsin, Michigan, and New York. Soft white wheat has low protein and high yields. Subclasses are Soft White, White Club, and Western White wheat. Total acreage is about 8.3 million acres.

2.9.8 Nutritional Composition of Wheat

Wheat provides nearly 55% of carbohydrate and 20% of the food calories. It contains carbohydrate 78.10%, protein 14.70%, fat 2.10%, minerals 2.10% and considerable proportions of vitamins (thiamine and vitamin-B) and minerals (zinc, iron). Wheat is also a good source of traces minerals like selenium and magnesium, nutrients essential to good health. Wheat grain precisely known as caryopsis consists of the pericarp or fruit and the true seed. In the endosperm of the seed, about 72% of the protein is stored, which forms 8-15% of total protein per grain weight. Wheat grains are also rich in pantothenic acid, riboflavin and some minerals, sugars etc. The bran, which consists of pericarp testa and aleurone, is also a dietary source for fiber, potassium, phosphorus, magnesium, calcium, and niacin in small quantities.

The kernel of wheat is a storehouse of nutrients essential to the human diet. Endosperm is about 83% of the kernel weight; it is the source of white flour. The endosperm contains the greatest share of the protein in the whole kernel, carbohydrates, iron as well as many B-complex vitamins, such as riboflavin, niacin, and thiamine. Bran is about 14.5% of the kernel weight.

Bran is included in whole-wheat flour and is available separately. Of the nutrients in whole wheat, the bran contains a small amount of protein, larger quantities of the B-complex vitamins listed above, trace minerals, and indigestible cellulose material called dietary fiber. Wheat germ is the embryo of the wheat kernel. The germ or embryo of the wheat is relatively rich in protein, fat and several of the B-vitamins. The outer layers of the endosperm and the aleurone contain a higher concentration of protein, vitamins and phytic acid than the inner endosperm. The inner endosperm contains most of the starch and protein in the grain. It is separated from wheat being milled for flour. Wheat germ is sodium and cholesterol free, and dense in nutrients. It is rich in vitamin E, magnesium, pantothenic acid, phosphorus, thiamin, niacin and zinc. It is also a source of coenzyme Q10 (ubiquinone) and PABA (para-aminobenzoic acid). Wheat germ is also high in fiber, and contains approximately 1 gram of fiber per tablespoon. A diet high in fiber can be useful in regulating bowel function (i.e. reducing constipation), and may be recommended for patients at risk for colon disease, heart disease, and diabetes.

2.9.9 Health Benefits of Wheat

- **Tooth Disorders**

Wheat is valuable in the prevention and cure of pyorrhea. It takes time to eat wheat and as it is generally taken with other foods, it compels the chewing of other foods also. This not only provides the needed exercise for the teeth and gum but also a great aid to digestion. Wheat grass juice acts as an excellent mouth wash for sore throats and pyorrhea. It also prevents tooth decay and tooth aches. Therefore, it is beneficial to chew wheat grass which draws out toxins from the gums and thus checks bacterial growth.

- **Internal Rejuvenation**

Wheat protein, which comprises up to eight per cent of the grain, has a special benefit as it has eight of the essential amino acids in delicately balanced proportions. A complete internal rejuvenation takes place when Wheat protein is metabolized into health-building amino acids. These amino acids build a resilient muscle that comes back to its original form after stretching and bending, healthy skin and hair and clearer eyesight and nourish the heart and lungs, tendons and ligaments, brain, nervous system and glandular network.

The B-complex vitamins, especially thiamin, riboflavin and niacin offered by natural brown Wheat promote youthful energy and nourishment to skin and blood vessels. An abundance of minerals in natural brown Wheat help to nourish the hormonal system, heal wounds and regulate blood pressure. Wheat also offers iron to enrich the bloodstream and phosphorus and potassium to maintain internal water balance along with other nutrients. Wheat thus helps restore internal harmony.

- **Constipation**

The bran of wheat, which is generally discarded in milling of the flour, is more wholesome and nourishing than the flour itself. It is an excellent laxative. The laxative effects of bran are much superior to those of fruits or green vegetables as cellulose of the latter is more easily broken down by bacteria while passing through the intestine. The bran is highly beneficial in the prevention and treatment of constipation due to its concentration of cellulose which forms a bulk-mass in the intestines and helps easy evacuation due to increased peristalsis.

- **Skin Diseases**

It has been scientifically proved that chlorophyll arrests growth and development of harmful bacteria. Wheat grass therapy can be effectively used for skin diseases and ulcerated wounds as by retarding bacterial action, it promotes cell activity and normal re-growth. By drinking wheat grass juice regularly, an unfavorable environment is created for bacterial growth. Poultice of wheat grass juice can be applied on the infected area, as it is an able sterilizer. Externally, wheat flour is useful as a dusting powder over inflamed surface as in burns, scalds and various itching and burning eruptions, Whole wheat flour, mixed with vinegar, boiled and applied outwardly removes freckles.

- **Digestive System Disorders**

Wheat grass juice used as an enema helps detoxify the walls of the colon. The general procedure is to give an enema with lukewarm or Neem water. After waiting for 20 minutes, 90 to 120 ml of wheat grass juice enema is given. This should be retained for 15 minutes. This enema is very helpful in disorders of the colon, mucous and ulcerative colitis, chronic constipation and bleeding piles.

- **Circulatory Disorders**

The chlorophyll content present in wheat enhances heart and lung functions. Capillary activity also increases while toxemia or blood poisoning is reduced. Due to increased Iron content in the blood and hemoglobin, lungs function better. Oxygenation improves and the effect of carbon dioxide is minimized. It is for this reason that wheat grass juice is prescribed for circulatory disorders.

2.9.9.1 Wheat Flour

Wheat flour is the product obtained by grinding wheat kernel or berries. The kernel consist of three distinct parts, bran, the outer covering of the grains germ, the embryo contained inside the kernel and endosperm the part of the kernel that makes white flour during milling, the three parts are separated and recombined accordingly to achieve different types of flours. This has no effect on nutrient and vitamin value. The only loss is a minute amount of vitamin E.

There are six different classes of wheat; hard red winter, hard red spring, soft red winter, hard white, soft white, and durum. The end products are determined by the wheat characteristics, especially protein and gluten content, the harder the wheat the higher the protein content in the flour. Soft low protein wheat is used in cakes, cookies and oriental noodles. Hard high protein wheat is used in breads and quick breads. Durum is used in pasta and egg noodles.

2.9.9.1.1 Nutritional Value of Wheat Flour

Wheat flour is an excellent source of carbohydrate depending on the flour all types of wheat flour derive at least 80% of their calories from carbohydrate, depending on the flour type percent of calories from protein range from 9-13% except from gluten flour which has 45% protein content. The calories of fat are never more than 5%.

Table 2.1: Nutritional composition of wheat flour per 100g edible portion

NUTRIENT	EDIBLE PORTION (100g)
Protein	12.6
Fat	2.0
Carbohydrate	68.5
Starch	66.8
Total sugar	1.7
Vitamin E	0.6
Thiamine	0.30
Riboflavin	0.07
Niacin	1.7
Folate	51

2.9.9.2 Types of wheat flours

- **White flour:** It is a finely ground endosperm of the wheat kernels.
- **All Purpose flour:** Is a blended wheat with a protein content lower than bread flour, ranging between 9% and 12% depending on brand or the origin where it is purchased, it may be composed of all hard or soft wheat, but it may be usually added or blend of the two and can range from 1% protein content to moderately high. It is marketed as an inexpensive alternative to baker's flour which is acceptable for most household baking needs.
- **Bread flour:** Is always made from hard usually hard spring wheat. It has very high protein content between 10% and 13% making it excellent for yeast bread baking. It can be white or whole wheat or in between.
- **Cake flour:** Is finely milled white flour made from soft wheat. It has very low protein content between 8% and 10% making it suitable for soft textured cakes and cookies. The higher protein content of the other flour would make the cake tough. American cake flour is bleached; in countries whose bleached flour is prohibited plain flour can be treated in a domestic microwave to improve the texture of the end product.
- **Pastry:** It has higher protein content than cake flour but lower than all-purpose flour. Its protein content ranges between 9% and 10%. The flour is shaken through a sieve to reduce the amount of lump for cooking pastry.
- **Self rising flour:** It is also referred to as a phosphated flour condolence biscuit and quick breads but is not recommended for yeast breads one cup of self-rising flour contains 1^{1/2} teaspoon baking powder and half (1/2) teaspoon salt. Self-rising can be substituted for all-purpose flour by reducing salt and baking powder according to these proportions.

CHAPTER THREE

3.0

MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Materials

Source of materials: The beetroot and wheat flour used for this work were obtained from ShopRite, Ilorin, Kwara state. Other ingredient such as vegetable oil, margarine, sugar, baking powder, eggs etc were also obtained from Owode market, Offa, Offa Local government Area, Kwara state, Nigeria.

3.1.1 Equipment

The equipments used such as baking oven, weighing balance, bowl, cake mixer, stainless tray, aluminium foil, measuring cylinder, hot air oven, measuring cup, measuring spoon, cutting knife etc were obtained from Processing Laboratory, Food Technology, Federal Polytechnic, Offa, Kwara state, Nigeria.

3.2 Methods

3.2.1 Unit operation for the heat-treated (blanched) beetroot powder

Grading: The fresh red beetroot obtained were graded according the parameters of bruiseness, spotless to select the wholesome materials from the whole lot

Washing: The best selected beetroots were washed with clean tap water to remove the accumulated dust from the vegetables plants.

Peeling: The beetroots were peeled to the bark from the roots using a clean knife

Slicing: The washed fresh beetroots were sliced into round tiny shape by reducing to size (1-3 mm) using sharp knife.

Blanching: The Fresh beetroots were blanched using different temperature and time of 95 °C to 115 °C, as well as in different times 40, 50 and 60 minutes.

Oven- Drying: The sliced beetroot were dried in hot air oven at 65 °C for about 8 h.

Grinding: The dried beetroot slices were subjected to grinding in grinder.

Sieving and Packaging: The ground material was passed through 60 mesh sieve and packed in High Density Polyethylene bags, sealed and stored for further use.

Fig. 3.1: Flow chart for the preparation heat – treated beetroot powder

Source: (Vujadinović, *et al.*, 2014)

3.2.2 Unit operation for the production of cake

Weighing of ingredients: All the ingredients such as wheat flour, sugar, margarine etc were weighed appropriately by using standard weighing balance.

Pre-Mixing: The weighed ingredient such as sugar and margarine were primarily mixed together thoroughly and later introduced flour to form paste dough.

Homogenizing: The mixed pasted were homogenized by using an electric homogenizer in order to get smooth, uniform and fluffy cake.

Panning: The homogenized cake pastes were put into the cake baking pan for proper baking.

Baking: The cake pastes were introduced into baking oven and baked at temperature of 230°C for 30 minutes until golden brown colour was shown.

Cooling and Packaging: The baked cake was then cooled at room temperature and packed inside polyethylene nylon for further analysis.

Fig. 3.2: Flow chart for the preparation of cake

Source: Ceserani and Kinton (2008)

3.2.3 Sample formulations

Sample A = 100% wheat flour cake

Sample B = Raw beetroot cake

Sample C = blanched beetroot cake at 65 °C for 40 minutes

Sample D = blanched beetroot cake at 85 °C for 40 minutes

Sample E = blanched beetroot cake at 100 °C for 40 minutes

3.3 Methods of Analysis

3.3.1 Sensory evaluation

The method of Larmond (2007) was used for sensory evaluation. The samples of cake were subjected to sensory evaluation with 100% wheat flour cake (100% WWFC) as control. A nine-member experienced panelist drawn from Food Science and Department, Federal Polytechnic, Offa was used to evaluate the samples. The panelists rated the samples for colour, smell, flavor, taste, texture, and overall acceptability using 9-point hedonic scale, where 9 was extremely acceptable and 1 was extremely unacceptable.

3.3.2 Proximate

Proximate composition was analyzed according to the official method of analysis described by the Association of Official and Analytical Chemist (AOAC, 2012).

3.3.2.1 Determination of Moisture content

The moisture content was determined by oven drying method. About 5g of each sample was weighed using analytical balance into previously weighed Petri-dishes (W). The weighed samples in the petri dish was allowed to dry in an oven at 105⁰C for 3hours. The samples were removed and cooled in desiccators to room temperature and the weight was noted, then it was returned into the oven at 105⁰C for 30min until a constant weight was obtained for each sample. The differences in weight between each Petri-dish and dried residue was recorded as the percentage of the initial sample. The percentage moisture was calculated as:

$$\% \text{ moisture content} = \frac{W1 - W2}{W_s} \times 100$$

Where

W = Initial weight of crucible + Sample

W1 = Final weight of crucible + Sample

Ws = Weight of sample

3.3.2.2 Determination of Protein content

0.5g of sample was weighed into a digestion flask and kjeldahl catalyst tablet was added, 10ml of conc.H₂SO₄ was added and digested for 4 hours until a clear solution was obtained (blue green color). The digest was cooled and transferred into 100ml volumetric flask and made up to mark with distilled water. 20ml of boric acid was dispensed into a conical flask and 5 drops of indicator and 75ml of distilled water was added to it. 10 ml of the digest was dispensed into Kjeldahl distillation flask, the conical and the distillation flask were fixed in place and 20ml of 2% NaOH was added through the glass funnel into the digest. The steam exit was closed and timing started when the solution of the boric acid and indicator turned green. The distillation was

done for 15 minutes, and the distillate was titrated with 0.05NHCl solution till the appearance of pink color. A blank was also run through all steps as above.

Therefore, the crude protein content was determined by multiplying percentage Nitrogen by a constant factor of 6.25

i.e. $\% \text{ crude protein} = \% N \times 6.25$.

$$\%T o(\%N) = \text{titre Value} \times \text{Atomic mass of nitrogen} \times \text{Normality of HCl used} \times 4$$

3.3.2.3 Determination of Fat

Fat was determined by ether extract method using Soxhlet apparatus.

1g of sample was weighed and wrapped in filter paper, placed in fat free thimble plugged lightly with cotton wool and extracted with petroleum ether (N-Hexane) in soxhlet apparatus set up for 5 hours. Water and heater were turned on to start extraction. After 4-6 siphoning, ether was allowed to evaporate and beaker was disconnected before the last siphoning. Extract was transferred into clean glass dish with ether washing and evaporated ether on water bath. The residue extract in dish was then placed in an oven at 105°C for 2 hours and cooled in a desiccator and weighed. The fat content will be calculated as;

$$\% \text{ fat} = \frac{(\text{Weight of filter paper} + \text{weight of sample}) - \text{Weight of residue}}{\text{Sample weight}} \times 100$$

3.3.2.4 Determination of Ash content

Clean empty crucible was placed in a muffle furnace at 600°C for an hour, cooled in desiccator and weighed (W). One gram of each sample was weighed in crucible (W₂). The sample was ignited over a burner with the help of blowpipe until it is charred. Then the crucible was placed

in a muffle furnace set at 550⁰C and left for 12-24h. The appearances of gray white ash indicated complete oxidation of all organic matter in the sample. The crucible with the sample was cooled and weighed (W₃).The crucible with the sample was weighed and the percentage ash calculated

$$\text{as; } \% \text{ Ash content} = \frac{W_3 - W_1}{W_2} \times 100$$

Where W₃ = weight of the sample with crucible before ashing

W₂ = weight of the sample with crucible after ashing

W = weight of the sample

3.3.2.5 Determination of Crude fibre

About 5g of the sample was accurately weighed into flask; 200ml of running water and 1.25ml H₂SO₄ was added. The mixture was heated under reflux for 30 minutes. The hot mixture was filtered through a fibre muslin cloth. The obtained filtrate was thrown off and the residue was returned to the fibre flask of which 200ml of running water and 1.25g NaOH was added and heated for another 30 minutes. The residue was removed using N-hexane and ethanol and finally transferred into already weighed crucible. The crucible and the residue was oven dried at 105⁰C overnight to drive off the moisture. The oven dried crucible containing the residue was cooled in a dessicator and later weighed to obtain the W₁. The crucible with W₁ was transferred to the muffle furnace for ashing at 550⁰C for 4 hours. The crucible containing white or grey ash (Free of carbonaceous materials) was cooled in the desiccator and weighed to obtain W₂.

The difference W₁ – W₂ gives the weight of fibre.

$$\% \text{Fibre} = \frac{W_1 - W_2}{\text{weight of sample}} \times 100$$

3.3.2.6 Determination of carbohydrate content

The total carbohydrate was determined by difference. The sum of percentages moisture, ash, crude lipid, crude protein and crude fiber was being subtracted from 100%.

$$\text{Carbohydrate} = 100 - (\% \text{ moisture} + \% \text{ ash} + \% \text{ protein} + \% \text{ lipids} + \% \text{ fiber}).$$

3.3.3 Determination of Vitamins

Vitamin C, K, A, E content of the aqueous extract was determined using the method of Benderitter *et al.*, (1998). DNPH [2 g dinitrophenyl hydrazine, 230 mg thiourea and 270 mg $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in 100ml of 5 M H_2SO_4) was prepared and 75 μl were added to 150 μl of the extracts and then 100 μl 13.3 % trichloroacetic acid (TCA) and water was added. The reaction mixture was subsequently incubated for 3 h at 37°C, then 0.5 ml of 65 % H_2SO_4 (v/v) was added to the medium and the absorbance was measured at 520 nm in the Lab-Tech digital colorimeter, UK. The vitamin C content of the extracts was subsequently calculated using ascorbic acid as standard (10mg/100ml) as standard

3.3.4 Statistical analysis

All experiments including organoleptic analyses were replicated. The means and standard deviations (SD) were calculated taking all the readings into consideration. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences). One-way ANOVA (Analysis of variance at the level of significance $p \leq 0.05$) was performed using Duncan multiple range tests to ascertain the significance of the means.

CHAPTER FOUR

4.0

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Proximate properties of the samples

Table 4.1: The results of the proximate composition of the samples

Sample	Moisture	Ash	Fibre	Fat	Protein	Carbohydrate
A	10.41±0.39 ^a	0.87±0.05 ^c	1.95±0.01 ^c	31.19±0.27 ^d	17.13±0.02 ^b	38.43±0.57 ^b
B	11.33±0.86 ^a	0.55±0.08 ^a	2.85±0.03 ^d	25.13±0.48 ^c	18.14±0.08 ^d	46.27±0.34 ^d
C	12.89±0.93 ^b	0.61±0.04 ^{ab}	1.82±0.04 ^b	21.86±0.55 ^a	16.61±0.14 ^a	46.21±0.88 ^d
D	10.73±0.6 ^a	0.51±0.07 ^a	1.32±0.09 ^a	23.43±0.34 ^b	17.74±0.01 ^c	42.27±0.53 ^c
E	10.85±1.27 ^a	0.68±0.01 ^b	3.03±0.06 ^c	21.83±0.62 ^d	18.02±0.01 ^d	35.58±0.71 ^a

Means score having the same alphabet along the same row are not significantly different ($p \leq 0.05$), values are mean \pm standard deviation of triplicate determination.

KEYS

Sample A = 100% wheat flour cake

Sample B = Raw beetroot cake

Sample C = blanched beetroot cake at 65 °C for 40 minutes

Sample D = blanched beetroot cake at 85 °C for 40 minutes

Sample E = blanched beetroot cake at 100 °C for 40 minutes

The results of the proximate compositions of the samples are shown in table 4.1 above. The result of the moisture content of the samples ranged between 10.41 to 12.89%. Sample C (blanched beetroot cake at 65 °C for 40 minutes) had the highest value while sample A (100% wheat flour cake) had the least value for moisture content 10.41%. There was no significant ($p \leq 0.05$) difference among the samples except sample C (blanched beetroot cake at 65 °C for 40 minutes) which was significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) different from other samples. However, the moisture content of beetroot cakes were observed to be higher than control (100% wheat flour cake) which could be due the fact that beetroot has more natural moisture percentage as regards the vegetable. The results of the moisture content obtained from this work were higher where compared to the work of Prerna *et al.* (2018) reported 3.0-4.1% for the cracker from blends of wheat-beetroot flour. The moisture of the sample was also lower to the finding of Lucky *et al.* (2020) reported 22.58 to 23.40% for the production cake from beetroot flour blends. However, high moisture content has been associated with short shelf-life of cake or baked products, as they encourage microbial proliferation that lead to spoilage (Akhtar *et al.*, 2008).

The result of the ash content of the sample showed significant ($p \leq 0.05$) difference among the sample except sample B and D of (Raw beetroot cake and blanched beetroot cake at 85 °C for 40 minutes) which was not significantly different ($p \leq 0.05$) from others. Sample A (100% wheat flour cake) was observed to having the maximum value of 0.87% and sample D (Blanched beetroot cake at 85 °C for 40 minutes) having the minimum value ash content of 0.51%. There was significant reduction in the beetroot cakes sample compared in the control of 100% wheat flour. This could be due to the heat-treatment the samples were subjected to. The result of the ash content of this work were similar when compared to 0.52-0.88% obtained from Vujadinovic *et*

al., (2014) in heat-treated beetroot flour cake but higher than (1.02-2.84%) reported by Lucky *et al.* (2020).

The result of the crude fibre of the samples ranged between 1.32 to 3.03%. Sample E (100°C for 40min) had the highest value while sample D (Blanched beetroot cake at 85 °C for 40 minutes) had the least value of fibre. There were significant ($p \leq 0.05$) differences among the entire samples. The values of fibre obtained from this work were higher than 0.03 to 1.90% reported by Murlidhar *et al.* (2016) reported for blanched beetroot cookies. Fibre is important for the removal of waste from the body thereby preventing constipation and many health disorders (Aleixandre and Mighel, 2008).

The fat content of the samples were significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) from each others. The result of the cake sample ranged between 21.83-31.19%. Sample A (100% wheat flour cake) had the highest value while sample E (Blanched beetroot cake at 100 °C for 40 minutes) had the lowest score of crude fat. The total decrease in the blanched samples could be due to the different temperature the samples were subjected to. From the literatures, beetroot has been recognized as low fat plant (Ellench *et al.*, 2011). The fat content reported for this work was in agreement with report of Kohajdova *et al.* (2018). The high oil content of cake will affect their shelf-life food with high fat supply thrice the amount of energy required by the body (Wardlaw, 2004).

The protein content of the sample ranged from 17.13 to 18.14%. Sample B (Raw beetroot cake) had the highest value while sample C (Blanched beetroot cake at 65 °C for 40 minutes) had the least value of 16.61%. There was significant increase in beetroot sample substitute, but higher in the sample B (Raw beetroot cake). The total increase in sample B could be due to the heat-treatment the other beetroot sample were subjected to which could have altered their protein

content. The results of protein content obtained from this work were higher when compared to 13.15-15.83% of steamed beetroot cake reported by Nazri and Karuna Thara (2011). Protein is a major nutrient needed as building blocks for the body, necessary for growth and for the repair of damaged tissues (Wardlaw 2004).

The carbohydrate content of the sample ranged from 35.58 to 46.27%. Sample B (Raw beetroot cake) had the highest value while sample E (Blanched beetroot cake at 100 °C for 40 minutes) had the least value respectively. There was significant ($p \leq 0.05$) difference among the sample except sample B and C which were not significantly different from each other. The results of carbohydrate content obtained from this work were lower when compared to 62.24-66.70% report of Murlidhar *et al.* (2016).

4.2 Vitamin composition of the samples

Table 4.2: The results of the vitamin composition of the samples

Sample	Vitamin A	Vitamin E	Vitamin C	Vitamin K
A	25.628±0.005 ^a	0.0658±0.005 ^b	1.138±0.06 ^a	0.002±0.001 ^a
B	38.097±0.78 ^b	0.0414±0.03 ^{ab}	4.219±0.057 ^c	0.004±0.001 ^{ab}
C	56.30±0.869 ^c	0.0373±0.004 ^a	7.594±0.057 ^d	0.006±0.004 ^b
D	79.31±0.80 ^d	0.0341±0.0043 ^a	2.263±0.06 ^b	0.002±0.001 ^a
E	37.58±0.802 ^b	0.043±0.005 ^{ab}	4.18±0.14 ^c	0.015±0.001 ^c

Means score having the same alphabet along the same row are not significantly different ($p \leq 0.05$), values are mean \pm standard deviation of triplicate determination.

KEYS

Sample A = 100% wheat flour cake

Sample B = Raw beetroot cake

Sample C = blanched beetroot cake at 65 °C for 40 minutes

Sample D = blanched beetroot cake at 85 °C for 40 minutes

Sample E = blanched beetroot cake at 100 °C for 40 minutes

The result of the vitamin A content of the sample ranged from 25.628 to 79.31mg/100g. Sample D (Blanched beetroot cake at 85 °C for 40 minutes) had the highest value while sample A (100% wheat flour) had the least value of vitamin A content. The result showed significant ($p \leq 0.05$) difference between the entire samples. However, there was significant increase of vitamin A with addition of beetroot irrespective of heat-treatment used. These indicate the level of vitamin A content present in beetroot compared to whole wheat (Daniela *et al.*, 2014). The result of vitamin A content obtained from this work were lower when compared to (30.68-82.65mg/100g) of beetroot cake reported by Vujadinovic *et al.*, (2014). Vitamin A is needed for the major growth and functioning of many part of the body system (Kovalcora *et al.*, 2015).

The result of the vitamin E content of the cake samples ranged from 0.043 to 0.0658mg/100g. Sample E (Blanched beetroot cake at 100 °C for 40 minutes) had the least value while sample A (100% wheat flour) had the highest value of vitamin E. Sample C, D and B, E were not significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) different from each other meanwhile sample A (100% wheat flour). There was significant ($p \leq 0.05$) difference this could be due to the fact that beetroots are literally low in vitamin E compared to whole-wheat. However, beetroot has been reported of high value of vitamin E (67.8mg/100g) compared to wheat flour (Dias *et al.*, 2009). The value of vitamin obtained from these work were significantly lower when compared value (0.82-1.23mg/100g) obtained from beetroot supplement cookies by (Murlidhar *et al.*, 2016). The vitamin E is considered as biological antioxidant and play principal role in fertility (Martinez- Vallalenga, 2006).

The result of the vitamin C content of the sample ranged from 1.138 to 7.594mg/100g. Sample C (Blanched beetroot cake at 65 °C for 40 minutes) had the highest value while sample A (100% wheat flour cake) had the least value of vitamin C 1.138mg/100g. There was significant decrease

in the increased of the blanching temperature which could lead to the leaching of the vitamin. However, the significant ($p \leq 0.05$) differences occurred among the entire samples. The result of vitamin C content obtained were higher when compared to (0.025-0.029mg/100g) reported by (Kavalcova *et al.*, 2015). Hence, vitamin C is an essential nutrient involved in repair of tissue and the formation of collagen (Jastrebova *et al.*, 2003).

The result of the vitamin K content of the sample ranged between 0.002 to 0.015mg/100g. Sample E (Blanched beetroot cake at 100 °C for 40 minutes) had the maximum value which sample A and D of 100% wheat flour and 85°C for 40 min had the minimum value of vitamin K content respectively. There was no significant ($p \leq 0.05$) difference among the sample except sample A and D which are not significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) different from each other. The results of vitamin K obtained from these work was in agreement with (0.002-0.017mg/100g) reported by (Singh *et al.*, 2016). Vitamin K refers to a group of fat soluble vitamins that play a role in blood clotting, bone metabolism and regulating blood calcium level (Vali *et al.*, 2007).

4.3 Sensory evaluation of the samples

Table 4.3: The result of the sensory evaluation of the cake samples

Samples	Colour	Texture	Flavour	Appearance	Taste	Overall acceptability
A	8.0±0.82 ^a	7.8±1.03 ^a	7.7±1.25 ^a	8.4±0.84 ^a	6.7±1.42 ^a	8.4±0.84 ^a
B	7.6±1.43 ^a	7.9±1.45 ^a	7.3±1.06 ^a	7.4±1.35 ^{ab}	6.3±1.16 ^a	8.2±1.03 ^a
C	7.2±1.14 ^a	7.3±1.25 ^a	7.3±1.06 ^a	6.80±1.48 ^a	6.5±1.18 ^a	7.9±1.29 ^a
D	7.6±0.97 ^a	7.6±0.7 ^a	7.4±1.35 ^a	7.3±0.82 ^{ab}	7.0±1.33 ^a	7.9±1.29 ^a
E	8.1±1.29 ^a	7.3±1.25 ^a	8.1±0.74 ^a	7.7±1.16 ^{ab}	7.3±1.25 ^a	8.1±1.10 ^a

Means score having the same alphabet along the same row are not significantly different ($p \leq 0.05$), values are mean \pm standard deviation of triplicate determination.

KEYS

Sample A = 100% wheat flour cake

Sample B = Raw beetroot cake

Sample C = blanched beetroot cake at 65 °C for 40 minutes

Sample D = blanched beetroot cake at 85 °C for 40 minutes

Sample E = blanched beetroot cake at 100 °C for 40 minutes

The sensory evaluations of the samples were shown in the table 4.3 above.

The taste of the samples revealed that samples ranged from 6.3 to 7.3. Sample C (Blanched beetroot cake at 65 °C for 40 minutes) had the highest mean value and samples E (Blanched beetroot cake at 100 °C for 40 minutes) having the least among all the samples. The taste of the sample shows no significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$) except sample A and C which were significantly different ($p \leq 0.05$) from other samples. Taste is one the main sensory attribute; determine by the tongue. This mostly determines the acceptance or rejection of the samples.

Colour is a major attribute of the products. This could vary based on the types and quality of ingredient or processing implored. However, Sample E (Blanched beetroot cake at 100 °C for 40 minutes) had the highest mean value of 8.1 while sample C (Blanched beetroot cake at 65 °C for 40 minutes) had the least value of 7.2. Samples were not significantly different from each other ($P \leq 0.05$). The variation between the colour of the samples could due to the addition of beetroot powder and heat treatment the samples were subjected to.

The appearance of the samples shows that sample A (100% wheat flour) had the highest values of 8.4 while sample B (Raw beetroot cake) had the lowest mean value of 7.3 among all samples. There was no significant difference ($P \leq 0.05$) among all the samples. The result of the appearance of the cake samples could be due to the addition of beetroot flour which could bring about differences of the cake produced.

Flavor is distinctive typical pleasant smell perceived by the olfactory sense. There was no significantly different ($P \leq 0.05$) from all other samples. The result of the sample ranges from 7.3 to 8.1. The result showed that sample B and C (Raw beetroot cake and blanched beetroot cake at

65 °C for 40 minutes) has the least value among the sample; while sample A (100% wheat flour cake) had the highest mean value.

Overall acceptability refers to the general acceptance of the product. Sample A (100% wheat flour) had the highest score, while Sample C (Blanched beetroot cake at 65 °C for 40 minutes) and D (Blanched beetroot cake at 85 °C for 40 minutes) had the least score. Samples were not significantly ($P>0.05$) different from each other. The highest values obtained from the overall acceptability of the sample show that the entire sample was wholesome. The variation between the cake samples could be due to the beetroot flour added.

CHAPTER FIVE

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Conclusion

Beetroot flour, an abundant source of dietary fibre and vitamin content can be used in the production of bakery and confectionery products. Protein, fat, ash and fibre contents of different percentages of beetroot flour cakes increased with the increase of treated beetroot flour. The samples showed higher value in term of vitamin content compared to control sample. The cake containing (100°C for 40min) blanched beetroot flour had a better colour, flavor, and overall acceptability compared to other cakes. This study suggested that cakes prepared with (100°C for 40min) blanched beetroot flour had comparatively better nutritional and sensory characteristics over control sample.

5.2 Recommendation

The beetroot cake produced showed good nutritional values. Therefore, cake with beetroot flour is advised to be consumed in our everyday diet for its health benefits. Thus, beetroot cake find new avenue for consumption among other healthy snacks.

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